

УДК 613

**THE PHILOSOPHICAL AND IDEOLOGICAL
UNDERSTANDING OF HUMAN DEVELOPMENT AND
THE FORMATION OF HIS HEALTH**

Maria Goncharenko

V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University (Kharkov,
Ukraine)

As the title implies the article describes the philosophical and ideological notion of human development, the evolution of human body representations and its health, the impact on human health of its interaction with the outside world and its spiritual component. It is spoken in detail about the idea of holographic mechanisms of human mind functioning, its structural energy organization, biochemical and biophysical mechanisms underlying wave operation, which is the fundamental basis for the formation of a new worldview that can create the theoretical basis of the health science, and the developing of some new diagnostic methods and the formation of human health.

It should be noted that each new era in the history of scientific ideas and methods bring us techniques that can help us to compile a full and complete picture of the universe and human in it. The new paradigm is based on the general scientific statement of the universal and inseparable connection of human and his environment, the availability of energy-information exchange between them. The current period contributes to their creative and transcendent ways of perceiving information. An important moment in the modern sense of the world order is the idea of the information field of the Universe.

The investigation of the wave properties of all living organisms can lead to the forming ideas justification about the structural organization of the human, consisting of the physical body and subtle bodies, including the sphere of etheric, the psychic, mental and spiritual bodies, which differ in their wave characteristics. Every organ and every cell has its own specific range of vibrations, its specific characteristics.

It is shown that new knowledge requires new approaches to the study. You need to know how the wave transmits information signal from the environment into the human body, how it transforms, how to determine the positive reactions of the body and harmonizing effect.

It is spoken in detail about the development of valeology that requires a serious theoretical foundation. First of all, it is necessary to improve the philosophical and ideological ways of research. This fundamental research should strive to know the laws of interaction between spiritual, mental and physical bodies, which is an important theoretical basis for

health sciences and the development of new methods of diagnosis, correction and rehabilitation.

Keywords: *energy-information levels of the human organization; wave processes; physical, mental, social and spiritual components of health.*

Formulation of the problem and its connection with important scientific tasks. According to existing ideas in the history of science, there are four major eras of changes that are accompanied not only by scientific discoveries, but also by changes in the theoretical approaches to the understanding and description of the structure of the Universe.

The first scientific revolution (XVII century), the classical mechanical science, has mechanics as a standard scientific theory. The basis of the mechanistic view of the world is the movement of atoms and bodies in absolute space over absolute time.

The second scientific revolution (the end of XVIII century – the first half of XIX century) is a classical disciplinary organized science. The third scientific revolution (the end of XIX century – the middle of XX century) is a non-classical science, cybernetics, a general systems theory that begins with the appearance of an electromagnetic picture of the world. The fourth scientific revolution (the last third of the XX century) is an after nonclassical science synergetics that opens a new object of knowledge: self-organizing and self-developing complex systems, which are a mandatory component of people. The leading motive is a statement of connectedness of everything with everything, the idea of presence of all in everything.

Each new era in the history of scientific ideas and methods brings us to compile a full and complete picture of the Universe and human in it.

Currently is being created a model of the Universe, the bases of which are:

- idea of its basic integrity;
- belief in the unity of subject and object of knowledge;
- in natural science studies the highlighting of the consciousness and recognition issues in the science methodology determines the role of intuition on the same level with the logic;

•returning to the scientific world the idea of the Creator, and the opening of a new level of consciousness evolution understanding, its place and role in the creation and development of the Universe.

The new paradigm is based on the general scientific statement of the universal and inseparable connection of human and his environment, the existence of energy information exchange between them, carried out cause and effect relationships, built on the basic categories of being: time, space and the human consciousness as a decisive factor of interaction and transformation. The new paradigm reveals man's responsibility for every thought, word, action that comes out all planes of Existence; for the World, which should be considered as a living fabric of Space-Time-Interaction that is sensitive to any movement of the living in it systems.

By itself this scientific paradigm is a reflection of social consciousness, associated with the metamorphosis of the mind thinking and mechanisms of human cognition. Energies of paradigm affect the inflow of fresh ideas and promote new ways of perceiving the world and the perception of a higher level of information. The ideological platform of a new paradigm is shaped up as a system of connections and communications in a cognition process.

Analysis of recent research studies and publications. The current period contributes to active and creative and transcendent ways of perceiving information. The transcendent way is a the process of setting and receiving the necessary information as a direct knowledge. It forms the understanding of the multidimensional nature of the information, the location of its fields on all levels of the Universe, where it forms certain information layers.

Life is a continuous process of development, self-improvement, self-realization of the program, inscribed by the Creator in which each level of Creation is a new fabric of life that has higher vibration energy saturation and potential, filled with new creative content and level of Consciousness. Every living system in accordance with the objectives of the concrete world develops the highest level of Consciousness, creativity and energy potential and performs the necessary work that contributes to the development of this sector of the Universe.

The doctrine of health has been existed in all ages of human development. For the first time the knowledge of the person and his health in order to create a new scientific field were summarized by I. I. Brehman. A serious contribution to the valeology development was made by V. P. Kaznacheev, G. L. Apanasenko, L. A. Popova, V. Lischuk, V. L. Kulinechenko, I. V. Muravov, E. G. Bulich, by Rostov Valeological school, V. V. Kolbanov, L. G. Tatarnikova, School of causality by V. P. Gocha, I. Gundarov, Kharkiv valeologists school.

The purpose of this paper is to examine how evolves conception of human, his health and interaction with the outside world in the scientific knowledge development and the reality of changing scientific paradigms. The possibility of opening by a person of committed knowledge of the world is carried out by a long Learning. The path of knowledge is revealed in a new vision of reality that leads to a change of the existing scientific paradigm.

As the birth of valeology was proclaimed by I. I. Brehman in 1980 s, this period can be attributed to the transition from the stage of non-classical period to the period of after non-classical science. In general, the development of valeology can be shown in the form of the scheme where the first stage of knowledge of human health is focused on the study of development patterns and functioning of the body (the period of classical science). The second step carries out in-depth study of regularities of mental health component (the period of non-classical science). At the third stage of the current knowledge about the health of a significant spiritual component is focused on health and its role in the management hierarchy of this process (the period of after nonclassical science).

An important moment in the modern sense of the world order is the idea of the Universe information field: it is layered, structurally resembles a russian doll (matrioshka), nonlocal. These are the layers of different densities and each of the lying above layer penetrates all lower ones and hierarchically links up with higher layers to the very Absolute (*scheme 1*).

At the core of understanding the interaction between the layers is the theory of interaction of wave processes. The layers of different density of energy

are energy fields that generate waves of different frequencies of vibration. Such media, as the torsion fields created in the small world not series of levels, but series of spirals with different fineness and vibrations of different frequencies. Wave processes are characterized by a length, frequency, shape, period.

Scheme 1. The perception and the reality of opening

At the level of an integrated body system of all its components and its electromagnetic energy fields are summed up in the subtle energy bodies. The total process of the human body functioning is a cycle of wave interaction and particle properties of matter in space-time, i. e. the interaction of the subtle and the physical way. Complication concepts of wave interactions is realized through dissipative structures, the bifurcation points provide transferring of the information, new emergent properties, changes in the ratio of entropy that is

non-entropy. A significant development has been reached by an understanding of the resonance wave interactions mechanism.

A study of all living organisms wave properties has led to the justification of forming ideas about the structural human organization that consists of the physical (solid) and thin bodies, including the sphere of etheric, psychic, mental and spiritual bodies, which differ in their wave characteristics.

All the media have a wave nature of different lengths and frequency and develop in space and time like nonlinear (fractal) things. Information-frequency resonance matrix is a structured set of two components:

- a certain amount of perceived object information;
- a set of patterns of information resonant frequency response from the object.

A healthy person is characterized by the harmonious interaction of the physical and subtle plan, i. e. spirit, soul and body. This principle is based on a new understanding of the world order. From this pattern follows a hierarchical principle of the health building one of the main principles of valeological spirit roles management in interaction of a three-pronged structures: spirit, soul and body. At each level of functioning matter: information, energy, real there are different levels of organization of matter and, consequently, their patterns of interactions (*scheme 2*).

Scheme 2. Metastructures of relationship between Nature, Knowledge and Human

The primary research material. From the data was obtained follows that every organ and every cell has its own specific range of vibrations, its specific characteristics of these oscillations (form, view, and frequency). Maintenance of these oscillations depends on the "quality factor" of the resonator. If the "Q-factor" is broken or distorted, it may be incoherent, inadequate, pathological electromagnetic oscillations. In the case where an existing mechanism of self-improvement in the body is not able to degrade these fluctuations a disease comes out.

Pathological fluctuations can be eliminated by using external electromagnetic oscillations. In a healthy organism is maintained relative balance of electromagnetic waves that make up the homeostasis and with pathological abnormalities can be observed violations of the vibrations of harmony. The offset in the frequency band may occur in the higher frequencies and lower frequencies.

According to modern views the formation of pathological process develops in time according to the following stages:

- the first stage is a temporary disparity between various levels of functioning of biological systems;
- the second stage is a violation of information flow in the body in a functional mode voltage at stress or chronic fatigue syndrome. Recovery is possible with the active participation in the recovery process of the patient;
- the third stage is the metabolic energy, energy circulation disturbance. To restore the balance it is necessary to carry out therapeutic procedures;
- the fourth stage is a metabolic disorder and destruction of structures. Chronic diseases. Upon further displacement frequency can be shown degeneration of the organ and tissue death.

Based on the idea of the development of the pathological process in the human body, it can be argued that the health is a dynamic, non-local, harmonize spectrum of wave processes of various human organs and systems. Scheme 3 is

a multi-dimensional energy-system of the person that reflects the interaction of its subtle bodies with physical body (*scheme 3*).

Creating the energy structure of the subtle body precedes the formation of the physical body and manages its development, i. e. it is a "process map", according to it our body develops. Changes in the structure of thin bodies are transferred to the physical body through the meridians. Meridians are a kind of "channels" or "doors" between the physical and subtle bodies. A state of energy-structural organization of the person is determined by the methods infodiagnostic. Information and energy exchange with the environment through energy centers that called chakras.

Scheme 3. A multidimensional human energy system

Methods of infodiagnosics are methods that explore the process of information exchange in the body (receiving, encoding, transmission, decoding, storing information). Currently we can distinguish such methods:

- the physical, this is the therapeutic examination;
- laboratory, this is a study of concentration and ratios of hormones; immunnogram etc.;

- studying of the content of biologically active substances;
- hardware, these are electroacupuncture diagnostics (Voll, Nakatani et al.); electrocardiography, electroencephalography, electromyography, computer diagnostics on Hardware-software complex “KSD”, “INTA-com-Voll” and others.

Informotherapy is an area of valeological knowledge that studies the impact of information on the physiological, biochemical, biophysical and pathological processes in the human body, the processes of receipt, encoding, storing, decoding and use of the information.

Self-regulation of physiological functions is the automatic maintenance of a vital factor of the organism on a constant level.

In addition to self-regulation wave correction of health process can be used.

Currently, the knowledge of the mechanisms of health wave correction methods studied deep enough:

- bioresonance therapy (BRT) this is the treatment with a single fixed (permanent) frequency;
- multiresonance therapy (MRT) this is a treatment with a few fixed frequencies simultaneously;
- mora therapy treats by complex electromagnetic spectrum;
- interference therapy this is a treatment based on interaction between internal and external frequencies that are not synchronized in time;
- informotherapy (IT) this is a treatment deployed in time with sequences of frequencies and spectra, structured on the basis of cellular languages.

In accordance with the structural organization of human, health is evaluated separately at different levels of organization, i. e. at the physical level, mental, spiritual and social levels.

Resonance correction does not treat organs or organ system, it updates a portrait energetic and healthy person using the information in the passage of a corrective body structure, harmonizing the movement of energy within the body, using the body's ability to regulate itself.

All the media have a wave nature of different lengths and frequency and can develop in space and time in nonlinear (fractal) way. Getting by the object information codes leads him to producing some set of feasible actions. This complex consists of changes in the parameters of the internal state of an object, and changes in its external manifestations (interaction with the objects of the environment). The principle of expediency includes the principle of timeliness of each action separately and matching them on time in the complex.

Conclusions and prospects for further development. New knowledge requires new approaches to the study. On the one hand, it is necessary to know how the wave data signal is transmitted from the environment into the human body, how to carry out the transformation of it, how to determine the positive reactions of the body and to reveal this harmonizing effect. On the other hand, it is important to know the mechanisms of transformation of the information signal at the borderline between interface and body, at the level of the cell plasma membrane.

According to the above, the development of valeology requires a serious theoretical foundation. First of all, it is necessary to improve the philosophical and ideological direction. This fundamental direction should strive to know the laws of interaction of spiritual, mental and physical bodies, which are an important theoretical bases for health sciences and the development of new methods of diagnosis, correction and rehabilitation.

The leading role in the development of this process is given to study, knowledge and awareness of the spirituality role in the formation of health, moral and ethical perfection, which are determined in the general health cultural level of the current human society.

References

1. Goncharenko M. Valeopedagogicheskie aspekty duhovnosti [Valeopedagogical aspects of spirituality]: V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine, 2007. – 400 p. (in Russian).
2. Goncharenko M. Nauchnyie osnovyi sovremennogo mirovozzreniya. Valeologicheskiy aspekt [Scientific foundations of the modern world.

Valeological aspect]: V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine, 2012. – 256 p. (in Russian).

3. Golovakha M. Informodiagnostika i informoterapiya [Informodiagnosics and informotherapy]: "Dorado-Druk", 2010. – 128 p. (in Russian).

4. Krause T. Universe. Mirozhdanie. Istoki znaniy i dialektika soznaniya. [The origins of knowledge and the dialectic of consciousness.] "Sloboda", 2005 – 536 p. (in Russian).

5. Popova L. Phoilosophiya zdovovya. [Philosophy of Health.] News of V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine, 2014, №1139. – 138. (in Russian).

ФІЛОСОФСЬКО-СВІТОГЛЯДНІ УЯВЛЕННЯ ПРО РОЗВИТОК ЛЮДИНИ ТА ФОРМУВАННЯ ЇЇ ЗДОРОВ'Я

М. С. Гончаренко

Робота висвітлює філософсько-світоглядне уявлення про розвиток людини, про еволюцію уявлення людини про свій організм і здоров'я, про вплив на здоров'я людини його взаємодії з навколишнім світом і його духовної складової. Дано уявлення про голографічні механізми функціонування свідомості людини, про його структурну енергетичну організацію, про механізми, що лежать в основі хвильового функціонування, які є фундаментальною основою формування нового світогляду для створення як теоретичної бази науки про здоров'я, так і для розробки нових методів діагностики й формування здоров'я людини.

Ключові слова: енерго-інформаційний рівень організації людини, хвильові процеси; фізична, психічна, соціальна й духовна складові здоров'я.

ФИЛОСОФСКО-МИРОВОЗЗРЕНЧЕСКОЕ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЕ О РАЗВИТИИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА И ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЕГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ

М. С. Гончаренко

Работа освещает философско-мировоззренческое представление о развитии человека, об эволюции представления человека о своем организме и здоровье, о влиянии на здоровье человека его взаимодействия с окружающим миром и его духовной составляющей. Дано представление о голографических механизмах функционирования сознания человека, о его структурной энергетической организации, о механизмах, лежащих в основе волнового функционирования, которые являются фундаментальной основой формирования нового мировоззрения для создания как теоретической базы науки о здоровье, так и для разработки новых методов диагностики и формирования здоровья человека.

Ключевые слова: энерго-информационный уровень организации человека, волновые процессы; физическая, психическая, социальная и духовная составляющие здоровья.